

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract:

Today, the interest of the young generation in learning foreign languages is increasing. Therefore, teaching a foreign language, including English, in secondary schools requires the use of interactive methods in lessons. This article is devoted to the effects of organizing lessons using interactive methods in English language classes of general education schools.

Key words: English language teaching, interactive teaching, interactive methods, information and communication technologies, interactivity

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In our country, significant work is being done on the formation of an information society and the introduction of the most advanced information and communication technologies in all fields. In particular, the capabilities of interactive services are highly valued in this process. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the concept of "interactive" is defined as based on the reception or transmission of information through a computer network.

Interactive consists of a set of scientific, technological, organizational, financial, commercial activities aimed at creating a new product, the purpose of which is to use and provide the accumulated knowledge, skills, technology and production tools for the large-scale production of this new product. Therefore, interactive in education is a set of scientific, technological, organizational, financial, commercial activities aimed at training new personnel, the purpose of which is to direct and provide the accumulated knowledge, skills, technology and production process to train new personnel for the national economy on a large scale. Therefore, pedagogical innovation is any pedagogical innovation aimed at training a new product, i.e. personnel, specialist, the purpose of which is to ensure high efficiency of the process. If we take the daily pedagogical activity of a teacher, innovation is equivalent to any innovation that the pedagogue introduces into his activity and is aimed at improving and ensuring the effectiveness of education. In fact, any innovation serves as a factor that ensures the development of society. Accordingly, pedagogic innovation, on the one hand, is the basis for traditional teaching with a new perspective and ideas. Innovation in education takes strength from tradition, but changes the content and essence of the educational process in new ways. Consequently, the innovation fundamentally rebuilds and ensures the quality of education.

Interactive methods help increase the effectiveness of English lessons. The main criteria of interactive education: conducting informal discussions, the opportunity to freely describe and express the educational material, the number of lectures is small, but the number of seminars is large, the creation of

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opportunities for students to take initiative, small group, large group, class team assignment, written work and other methods, which are of special importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work. Interactive methods:

- raising students' interest in learning English;
- bringing the work of a teacher in English closer to the real conditions of life;
- effective communication methods, i.e. proper formation of teacher-student and mutual communication skills;
- raising the process of mastering new theoretical knowledge and practical skills to a new level;
- increasing students' responsibility for the educational process.

Its effectiveness is higher than traditional methods such as interactive methods of teaching, explanation, instruction and use of tools.

There are many types of interactive training, which are selected according to the characteristics of the lesson topic and the intended goals, and are prepared accordingly. Specific requirements are placed on the students' readiness to participate in the interactive training, such as mastering the necessary knowledge for active participation in the training, readiness for communication, working in mutual cooperation, independent thinking, own opinion including free expression and advocacy skills and more. Effective use of time in training is a necessary condition. For this, it is necessary to correctly select and prepare the necessary tools, as well as clearly define the training providers and their tasks. There are specific differences between interactive methods and traditional teaching methods, and each teacher should compare these differences, their advantages and disadvantages in relation to each other, when choosing lesson planning and delivery methods. must be taken into account. In this case, the most suitable interactive for imparting new knowledge, forming skills, developing, strengthening, repeating knowledge, applying it in training, and taking into account the characteristics of the academic subject. or the correct choice of other methods is assumed. The use of correctly selected methods ensures that training is interesting and effective.

We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues in the United States of America and England:

- "Creative Problem Solving" to use this method, the beginning of the story is read and how it ends. the judgment of students is referred to;
- "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to riddles;
- "Quick answers" helps to increase the efficiency of the lesson;
- "Warm-up exercises" using various games in the classroom to make students interested in the lesson;
- "Pantomime" (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are performed and students are tired;
- The method of "a chain story" helps to develop oral speech of students.

Modern interactive methods in foreign language teaching methodology developed by scientists and compared to traditional methods it has been proven that the level of efficiency is higher. Interactive learning methods significantly

increases the knowledge potential of the process compared to traditional methods. Because, in interactive methods, the student thinks freely independently, works as a partner with the teacher.

The conclusion is that the students of the course actively participate in the process and learn to perceive foreign speech. Speaking and listening take up most of the learning time. This method involves the artificial recreation of the language environment. The purpose of the communicative method is to help students overcome the language barrier, to teach the participants of the course to speak the language first, and then to think in this language. This gives the teacher the opportunity to plan the teaching of different groups of students / learners with different needs, knowledge levels and worldviews. In short, the teacher who aims to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson will achieve his goal only if he skillfully uses interactive teaching methods.

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